

DEVELOPMENT OF A NEW TYPE OF HOUSEHOLD APPLIANCES – REFRIGERATORS WITH A HEATING CHAMBER

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ABSTRACT

The object of this study is absorption-type refrigeration appliances, which allow to expand the functionality of household appliances without additional energy consumption.

Investigated problem: The aim of this study: firstly, due to the novelty of the proposed technique, it was necessary to show the real possibility of obtaining the temperature level required for technological processes (up to 70 °C); secondly, taking into account the experience gained in experimental studies, it was necessary to propose new designs for solving the problems of refrigeration and heat treatment of food products and raw materials in domestic conditions.

The main scientific results: It is shown that the development of devices that combine the functions of refrigeration storage and heat treatment of food products, semi-finished products and agricultural raw materials can become a promising area for energy saving in household appliances. In such household combined appliances, the heat released during the implementation of the refrigeration cycle is not immediately removed to the environment, but is transferred to a special heating chamber, while the temperature in the volume of the heating chamber is maintained higher than the air temperature in the room. The effect of energy saving is achieved by expanding the functionality of household appliances without attracting additional energy costs.

The original designs of combined absorption-type household appliances are proposed, a description of their operation, advantages and disadvantages, and areas of application are given.

The area of practical use of the research results: In the course of experimental studies, it was shown that the introduction of an additional heating chamber into the structure of household absorption refrigerators, thermally connected with the lifting section by the dephlegmator of the absorption refrigeration unit, does not lead to an increase in energy consumption (according to the test results below than in the standard version by 5 %) and does not impair the performance of the cooling chambers.

The area of practical use of the research results: household energy-saving appliances. Innovative technological product: the use of an evaporation-condensation cycle that provides highly efficient heat transfer at a distance of up to 1 meter from the heat dissipation zone of the refrigeration unit to the usable volume of the heating chamber of the household appliance.

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1. Introduction

1. 1. The object of research

The object of this research is absorption-type refrigeration appliances that allow to expand the functionality of household appliances without additional energy consumption.

1. 2. Problem description

The use of artificial cold is due to the need to reduce natural losses and extend the shelf life of food raw materials and finished products during transportation and storage [1].

For a long time, experts have concluded that the use of refrigeration technologies can reduce the loss of various types of products by 20–60 % and extend their shelf life by 2–10 times [2]. It has also been established that energy costs in the refrigeration storage of food raw materials and finished products are no more than 3–8 % of the total energy costs in the production of these products [3].

Absorption refrigeration appliances (ARA) occupy a special consumer niche in the modern world. They do not compete with compression counterparts in terms of energy performance, but are in demand among the population in case of special requirements for work and operating conditions [4, 5]. In particular, ARAs find demand in places where there are problems with the supply of electrical energy. This takes place in regions of the planet where there is no electricity supply or there are unstable sources of electricity, or in transport.

ARAs are unique in terms of the use of various sources of thermal energy. These are sources of alternating and direct electric current and burners for organic (natural and liquefied gas, kerosene, gasoline [4–6]) and thermal energy and solar radiation [7].

In most modern ARA models [4–6], there are possibilities to use three types of thermal energy sources: alternating electric current (when operating under normal conditions); direct electric current (when working on vehicles); burner in places where there are no stabilized power supplies.

The production of artificial cold in ARA is carried out by absorption refrigeration units (ARU), which do not contain moving elements (compressors and pumps) [4–7].

In this regard, ARAs are practically silent in operation, reliable, durable in operation and have the lowest cost among analogues. These points are also attracting the attention of consumers in the household refrigeration market. Quietness in operation is especially attractive for the hotel business, where ARA is almost indispensable.

The working fluid of ARU is a natural three-component mixture consisting of: ammonia as a refrigerant; water as an absorbent (absorbent); inert leveling gas (hydrogen or helium) [4–7]. Recently, in order to improve the energy efficiency of ARU, last time began to use a working ammonia-water mixture with the addition of an additional absorbent [8] and nanofluids [9].

An analysis of the ARU thermal regimes showed that a promising direction in energy saving could be the development of household appliances that combine the functions of refrigeration storage and heat treatment of food products, semi-finished products and agricultural raw materials.

In such combined household appliances, the heat released during the implementation of the refrigeration cycle is not removed to the environment, but is directed to a special heating (thermal) chamber (TC). In the volume of the TC, the temperature is maintained higher than the air temperature in the room.

The effect of energy saving is achieved due to the fact that the temperature conditions in the shopping center are maintained without attracting additional energy costs.

At the preliminary stage of the development of household combined appliances, an analysis was made of technologies using heat treatment of products, semi-finished products and raw materials. It was shown that for the implementation of the vast majority of food technologies in everyday life, the temperature range of 50...70 °C is sufficient [10].

In domestic refrigeration technology, such a temperature range of heat removal from the refrigeration cycle can only be obtained in ARU [11]. An analysis of the temperature fields of the heat-dissipating elements of the ARU showed that the required temperature potential (more than 70 °C) is possessed by the descending and ascending sections of the dephlegmator and the rectifier (**Fig. 1**).

The use of TC in domestic conditions is possible for heating the product to a given temperature and various types of technological processing, as a result of which a new product can be obtained (drying, fermentation, etc.).

In TC, it is also possible to refresh bread when it is heated to 60 °C – starch grains swell again and the elasticity of the crumb is restored.

The process of staling is also characteristic of dishes from cereals and pasta, even with short storage at room temperature. Heating these dishes to a temperature of 60 °C restores their original properties.

Along with heating dishes from cereals and pasta, TC can be used to heat the first and second courses. In this case, heating food is not associated with the danger of using open fire, which allows it to be produced by children of primary school age.

Fig. 1. Temperature fields of a typical ARU: R – rectifier-reflux condenser; K – capacitor; A – absorber; V – evaporator

Drying of fruits, vegetables, fish, medicinal herbs, berries, mushrooms at temperatures of 40...70 °C can be one of the important areas of TC application. Of particular interest at home is the drying of white roots, herbs, mushrooms and other vegetables, the drying of which in the autumn period is especially rational in TC.

It is also possible to dry and dry fish in TC.

It is also possible that TC can be used to soften butter and margarine when kneading various types of dough (33...35 °C), drying seeds, drying yeast, drying cereals to remove the bug, steaming herbal infusions, etc.

1. 3. Suggested solution to the problem

To solve these problems, various schemes of household appliances with additional TC have been developed, which differ in:

- a) heat transfer method – direct contact of heat-dissipating elements and TC (**Fig. 2**) [12], or the use of intermediate heat transfer devices (**Fig. 3**) – two-phase thermosyphons (TS) [12–14], including those with the effect “osmosis” [15];
- b) the location of the TC (on top of the refrigerator [12–14] and in the lower part [15]);
- c) TC design (single-chamber [11–13, 15] two-chamber [14]);

The simplest in design is the scheme with an intermediate heat transfer device, which involves a minimum of changes in the composition of the refrigeration apparatus and ARU. TS is attached to the lifting section of the dephlegmator in the area of the heat-insulating casing of the generator unit (**Fig. 4**).

In such a scheme, to reduce losses during heat transfer and to prevent condensation of ammonia, the entire dephlegmator and the TS transport zone are closed with a heat-insulating casing.

Fig. 2. Apparatus with direct contact of TC and ARU heat-dissipating elements (reflux condenser): 1 – TC; 2 – ARU evaporator; 3 – refrigerating chamber; 4 – generator unit; 5 – additional heat-insulating casing; 6 – ARU dephlegmator; 7 – ARU capacitor; 8 – contact zone of the ARU dephlegmator and the TC body

Fig. 3. TC with intermediate TS: *a* – TC section; *b* – design of thermal connection of the TC body and the TS condenser; 1 – TC cover; 2 – inner metal body of TC; 3 – thermal insulation of the TC body; 4 – outer body of the TC; 5 – heat-conducting paste; 6 – TS capacitor; 7 – TS capacitor substrate; 8 – threaded connections

Fig. 4. Absorption refrigeration apparatus with an additional heating chamber:
 1 – ARU generator unit; 2 – electric heater; 3, 4) – lifting section of the dephlegmator;
 5–7 – evaporation, transport, condensation section of the TS, respectively; 8 – heating chamber;
 9–11 – condenser, evaporator, ARU absorber, respectively

Two types of such household appliances have been developed, manufactured and studied – with air TC (**Fig. 5**) and liquid TC (**Fig. 6**). In the first case, heat from the heat-dissipating elements of the chamber is transferred to the objects of influence (food products) through the air, and in the second case, the object of influence is a liquid (food solutions such as mash, water for household purposes, etc.), which is poured into the TC through the top cover. Liquid TC is made in the form of a tank, the walls of which are thermally connected to the heat-dissipating elements of the ARU.

Fig. 5. Household appliance with air TC: 1 – refrigeration compartment; 2 – TC

Fig. 6. Household apparatus with liquid TC: 1 — refrigeration compartment; 2 – TC

2. Materials and Methods

Calculation of the design parameters of the NC was carried out according to the heat load on the lifting section of the dephlegmator 19...22 W.

The thicknesses of thermal insulation of the side walls, bottom and cover of the TC are determined as a result of mathematical modeling of non-stationary temperature fields.

This took into account:

- a) the orientation of the surfaces of the chamber and its thermal connection with the refrigerating chamber;
- b) design features of the TC (the air chamber is made in the form of a cabinet, and the liquid chamber is in the form of a chest);
- c) coefficient of working time CWT of the serial model of household single-chamber absorption refrigerator "Crystal-408" ASh-150.

Experimental designs were manufactured at the Vasilkovsky Refrigerator Plant (VRP). In all cases, the external geometric parameters of the TC were: height – 0.420 m; depth – 0.540 m; width – 0.570 m; useful volume – 35 dm³. Thermal insulation thickness: side walls – 0.080 m; bottom – 0.075 m; covers, rear and front walls – 0.10 m. In liquid TC, the inner case was made in the form of a complete body. Body material – stainless steel. The wall thickness of the body is 0.001 m. The wall thickness is 0.001 m.

A two-phase thermosiphon (TS) 1.200 m long and 0.010×0.001 m in diameter was used to provide thermal connection between the ARU dephlegmator lift section and TS. The TS body material is stainless steel. The heat carrier is ethyl alcohol. The TS was fastened to a dephlegmator with a diameter of 0.016×0.0014 m using a copper compression plate, and to reduce thermal resistance in the contact zone there was a compressed highly porous copper-based cellular material, the pores of which were filled with heat-conducting paste KTP-8 (**Fig. 7**).

Fig. 7. Scheme of fastening the TS to the ARU dephlegmator: 1 – TS; 2 – additional thermal insulation; 3 – thermal insulation of the ARU generator unit; 4 – zone of contact between the dephlegmator and the TS; 5 – lifting section of the dephlegmator; 6 – ARU capacitor

In all cases, the evaporator section of the TS was attached to the lower part of the reflux condenser lift section and installed parallel to it. The length of the TS evaporation section in the studies was varied by changing the zone of thermal connection with the reflux condenser. The TS transport zone was closed with a heat-insulating casing. The length of the condensation section of the TS did not change and amounted to – 0.3 m.

The study of thermal regimes of TC was carried out both in stationary (in “hard” conditions – $t_{o.c.} = 32\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, the coefficient of working time of the refrigeration appliance (CWT=1), and in transitional ($t_{o.c.} < 32\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, CWT<1) operating modes of the ARU.

3. Result

As a research result, the optimal length of the TS evaporative section was determined – 0.15 m. At the outlet of this section, the temperature of the dephlegmator is 73...76 °C.

The most favorable conditions for TC were regimes with elevated ambient temperatures, when heat losses are reduced, and the ARU CWT and, accordingly, the period of supply of heat load increases.

In connection with the insufficient value of the thermal power of the dephlegmator for heating water or other liquid in the TC, the operation of the apparatus in the thermostating mode was also stud-

ied. In this case, the water was heated to a temperature of 60 °C by a special electric heater, and after it was turned off, heat losses to the environment were compensated by heat supply from the reflux condenser, which made it possible to maintain the temperature in the TC in the range of 55...65 °C.

Taking into account the results of experimental studies, a variant calculation of the TC thermal insulation thickness was carried out. To create some margin, the calculation was carried out at $t_{o.c.}=20$ °C and CWT=0.55 and presented in the form of nomograms. Two options for thermal insulation were considered – polyurethane foam and fiberglass, while the outer width (0.570 m) and depth (0.54 m) were fixed, in accordance with the standard dimensions of the refrigerator.

The choice of a specific TC design is carried out taking into account the available heat load of the reflux condenser lifting section with a temperature level of 70 °C and above, while the variable parameters are: type of thermal insulation (cost); the value of the useful volume of TC; TC height (Fig. 8, a, b).

Fig. 8. Nomogram for determining the thickness of the thermal insulation (δ) of the heating chambers of the household absorption apparatus: *a* – depending on the useful volume (10...50 dm³) and the thermal load on the dephlegmator (thermal insulation material – fiberglass); *b* – depending on the value of the useful volume (10...50 dm³) and the heat load on the dephlegmator (thermal insulation material – polyurethane foam)

Based on the experience of practical developments and modeling of thermal regimes, a promising design of a household appliance with two TCs was developed on the basis of serial models of the VRP [16].

The device contains a vertical heat-insulated cabinet, divided into tiers into a refrigerating chamber (HK) 1, a low-temperature compartment (LTC) 2, TC 3 and TC with an increased, by 10...15 °C, compared to the ambient air temperature (KPTV) 4 .9).

Fig. 9. The design of a household appliance with two TCs based on an absorption refrigerator manufactured by: *a* – rear view; *b* – side view (section); 1 – TC; 2 – LTC; 3 – LC; 4 – KPTV; 5 – generator unit; 6 – dephlegmator; 7 – capacitor; 8,9 – evaporators; 10 – absorber; 11 – absorber tank; 12 – liquid heat exchanger; 13 – TS; 14 – TS capacitor; 15 – exhaust body; 16 – exhaust cavity; 18-21 – thermally insulated doors of cells.

An ARU is installed on the rear wall of the cabinet, including a hot unit 5, a dephlegmator 6, a condenser 7, a low-temperature 8 and a high-temperature evaporator 9 (LTE and HTE) installed in the LTC 2 and TC 1, respectively, an absorber 10, an absorber tank 11, a liquid heat exchanger 12.

A condenser section 14 TS 13 is installed on the rear inner wall of the TC, and the heating section (not shown in Fig. 9) is connected to the ARU dephlegmator in the volume of the heat-insulating casing of the hot unit 5.

A casing 15 is installed on the rear wall of the structure, forming an exhaust cavity 16, and TC 3 and KPTV 4 have exhaust cavities on the side walls (not shown in Fig. 9).

Chambers – TC 1, LTC 2, heating chamber 3 and KPTV 4 have separate heat-insulated doors 18, 19, 20, 21, respectively.

The proposed device works as follows.

In the process of ARU operation, artificial cold is produced in LTE 6 and HTE 9, while cooling of LTC 2 and TC 1 is provided. The implementation of the ARU refrigeration cycle is accompanied by heat dissipation into the environment from heat-loaded elements – dephlegmator 6, condenser 7 and absorber 10. Refrigerant vapor (ammonia) is cleaned from absorbent (water) vapor in dephlegmator 6 during the condensation process. The heat of the phase transition is transferred to the heating section of the TS, in which the heat carrier vapor is generated. The coolant vapor enters the condensation zone 14, where it is liquefied with the removal of the heat of vaporization into the heating chamber 3. This ensures the temperature regime of the chamber 3 at a level of up to 70 °C.

The presence of the casing 15 on the rear panel of the cabinet and at the side walls of the heating chamber 3 and KPTV 4 allows to organize exhaust cavities 16 and 17, which serve for in-

tensive air circulation. Absorber 10 is cooled in the forced draft mode created by condenser 7 and dephlegmator 6.

The heated air washes the side and rear walls of the heating chamber 3 and KPTV 4, reducing heat losses to the environment from the heating chamber 3 and heating the air in KPTV 4 by 10...15 °C compared to the ambient air temperature.

The experimental studies of the prototype showed that heat losses from TC decreased by 26 % at a chamber operating temperature of 70 °C and an ambient temperature of 26 °C, while the daily energy consumption of ARU was reduced by 15...20 %.

It should also be noted the development of an original design with a “diode” type TC (Fig. 10) [17].

Fig. 10. Apparatus with “diode” TC: a – general view of the apparatus; b – diagram of operation of “diode” TC; 1 – refrigerator; 2 – TC; 3 – generator; 4 – dephlegmator; 5 – capacitor; 6 – line of liquid ammonia; 7 – surge line; 8 – absorber; 9 – absorber tank; 10 – liquid heat exchanger; 11, 12 – TS condenser (evaporator); 13 – heat-insulating casing; 14 – TC internal cavity; 15 – TC heat insulation; 16 – additional “diode” TS; 17(18) – evaporator (condenser) of additional “diode” TS

The device contains a refrigerator 1 and a TC 2 installed on its top cover. ARU contains a generator 3, a dephlegmator 4, a condenser 5, a liquid ammonia line 6, an equalizing line 7, an absorber 8, an absorber tank 9, a liquid heat exchanger 10 and an evaporator (not shown in the **Fig. 10**).

The dephlegmator 4 ARU has a thermal connection with the TC, the condensation section 11 of which is fixed on the heat-dissipating surface of the TC 2. The evaporative section 12 of the TC is in thermal communication with the dephlegmator 4 of the ARU in the area covered with an insulating casing 13. The internal cavity 14 of the TC 2 is covered with thermal insulation 15.

In the volume of thermal insulation 15 there are additional “diode” two-phase thermosiphons (DTS) 16. The evaporating sections 17 of the DTS are thermally connected to the wall of the outer casing of the TC 2, and the condensation sections 18 to the walls of the internal cavity of the TC.

The device works as follows.

When the heat power is supplied to the generator 3, vapor is generated and the liquid solution is circulated. Circulation is carried out through the liquid heat exchanger 10 absorber 8 and the absorber tank 9. Steam containing mainly ammonia is supplied from the generator 3 to the dephlegmator 4. In the dephlegmator, water vapor is separated, which condense on the inner wall with the release of heat of vaporization. The condensate flows into the generation zone, and the purified ammonia vapor enters the ARU 5 condenser. The heat of reflux is transferred to the TS 12 evaporation zone, partially filled with a liquid heat carrier, where the heat carrier vapor is generated. The steam is transported to the condensation zone 11, thermally connected with the internal cavity 14 of the TC 2 and liquefies, giving off the heat of the phase transition of the TC 2. The condensate flows into the evaporation zone of the TS 12 and the evaporation-condensation cycle is repeated.

The ammonia vapor entering the condenser 5 is liquefied with the removal of the heat of vaporization to the environment. Condensate through line 6 enters the evaporator, where, evaporating into an inert gas environment, it provides the effect of artificial cooling. Stabilization of the supply of liquid ammonia to the evaporator is carried out using an equalizing line 7. The vapor-gas mixture saturated with ammonia enters the absorber tank 9, from where it rises countercurrently through the absorber 8 with a weak solution. ammonia solution. The purified gas-vapor mixture enters the evaporator, and the strong solution through the absorber tank 9 and the liquid heat exchanger 10 into the lower part of the generator 3. After that, the ARU cycle is repeated.

The internal cavity 14 of the TC 2 is filled with water, which must be heated for domestic needs, for example, for washing dishes in rural areas, where there is basically no hot water supply. Well or tap water, even in summer, has a temperature of 16...18 °C, and the ambient air temperature is 25...30 °C. The presence of a temperature difference of 10...15 °C between the outer casing and the inner cavity 14 causes the generation of coolant vapor, partially filling the evaporation zone 17 of the DTS 16. The coolant vapor enters the condensation zone 18 of the DTS 16, thermally connected with the walls of the internal cavity 14, where, liquefied, they give off the heat of vaporization ($Q_{o.c.}$) to heat the water filling the internal cavity 14. When the water is heated to a temperature equal to the ambient temperature and above, the DTS 16 “switches off”.

“Switching off” the DTS 16 is achieved by the fact that the coolant is concentrated in the evaporation zone 17, which has a lower temperature than in the condensation zone 18. Thus, the overturning of the evaporation-condensation cycle is achieved. It is possible to say that DTS 17 operates in the “thermal diode” mode.

The studies presented in this material were carried out on serial refrigeration equipment VRP, which is classified as an average (in terms of useful volume) class – 120...150 dm³.

In this regard, the question remains – how energy efficient will be the modernization of household refrigeration equipment of minimum (30...50 dm³) and maximum (180...300 dm³) volume.

In the future, the authors see the continuation of the studies presented in this paper in the study of the energy feasibility of installing TC in household absorption refrigeration appliances of small and large volumes.

In further developments, in order to effectively market new appliances, it would be advisable to get in touch with kitchen furniture designers and developers.

4. Conclusions

1. A promising area for energy saving in household appliances can be the development of devices that combine the functions of refrigeration storage and heat treatment of food products,

semi-finished products and agricultural raw materials. In such household combined appliances, the heat released during the implementation of the refrigeration cycle is not immediately removed to the environment, but is transferred to a special TC, while the temperature in the TC volume is maintained higher than the air temperature in the room. The effect of energy saving is achieved by expanding the functionality of household appliances without attracting additional energy costs.

2. For the implementation of the vast majority of food technologies in everyday life, the temperature range of 50...70 °C is sufficient. In modern household refrigeration equipment, only ARU can provide such a temperature range, while the lifting sections of the dephlegmator should be used as a source of heat load for an additional condenser.

3. Original designs of combined absorption-type household appliances are proposed, a description of their operation, advantages and disadvantages, and areas of application are given.

4. The results of experimental studies of household combined absorption-type appliances based on the serial model VRP "Crystal – 408" AIII –150 showed:

a) to reduce energy consumption during the start-up period, it is advisable to use additional sources of heat load to ensure acceptable thermal conditions of the TC, and this problem can also be solved using heat storage materials;

b) the introduction of an additional TC into the structure of household absorption refrigerators, thermally connected with the lifting section by the ARU dephlegmator, does not lead to an increase in energy consumption (according to the test results, it is lower than in the standard version by 5 %) and does not worsen the performance characteristics of the cooling chambers.

5. The results of calculating the thermal insulation parameters of additional TCs are given in the form of nomograms, according to which, depending on the thermal load of the lifting section of the ARU dephlegmator and the TC volume, one can find the thickness of the thermal insulation made of fiberglass or polyurethane foam. Calculations have shown that at an initial water temperature in the TC of 16 °C, an ambient temperature of 25 °C and a thermal power supplied from the dephlegmator 4 of the ARU – 10 W, 40 liters of water will be heated to a temperature of 50 °C 1.5 times faster, than in the absence of DTS connecting the inner cavity 14 with the outer casing.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in relation to this paper, as well as the published research results, including the financial aspects of conducting the research, obtaining and using its results, as well as any non-financial personal relationships.

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Data availability

There is no related data in the manuscript.

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